

Supplementary material

Localization of the acupuncture points used in the clinical cases.

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The descriptions and figures were retrieved from World Health Organization ¹.

Upper body points:

LI4: Hegu 合谷

On the dorsum of the hand, radial to the midpoint of the second metacarpal bone.

LI5: Yangxi 陽(阳)谿(溪)

On the posterolateral aspect of the wrist, at the radial side of the dorsal wrist crease, distal to the radial styloid process, in the depression of the anatomical snuffbox.

Note : The depression of the anatomical snuffbox is formed when the thumb is fully abducted and extended between the tendons of the extensor pollicis longus and the extensor pollicis brevis.

PC6: Neiguan 内关(关, 関)

On the anterior aspect of the forearm, between the tendons of the palmaris longus and the flexor carpi radialis, 2 B-cun proximal to the palmar wrist crease.

Note 1: With the fist clenched, the wrist supinated and the elbow slightly flexed, the two tendons become more prominent. PC6 is located 2 B-cun proximal to PC7. The posterior point corresponding to PC6 is TE5.

Note 2: If the palmaris longus tendon is not present, PC6 is medial to the flexor carpi radialis tendon.

PC7: Daling 大陵

On the anterior aspect of the wrist, between the tendons of palmaris longus and the flexor carpi radialis, on the palmar wrist crease.

Note: With the fist clenched, the wrist slightly flexed, the two tendons become more prominent. PC7 is located at the midpoint of the palmar wrist crease, between the tendons of palmaris longus and the flexor carpi radialis, at the same level as HT7, at the proximal extremity of the pisiform bone.

SI4: Wangu 腕骨(骨)

On the posteromedial aspect of the wrist, in the depression between the base of the fifth metacarpal bone and the triquetrum bone, at the border between the red and white flesh.

Note: With one finger placed on SI3, push and slide proximally along the fifth metacarpal bone to the bony projection, SI4 is located in the depression between these two bones.

TE4: Yangchi 陽(阳)池

On the posterior aspect of the wrist, in the depression ulnar to the extensor digitorum tendon, on the dorsal wrist crease.

Note 1: TE4 can be palpated when moving proximally along the gap between the fifth and fourth metacarpal bones, at the same level as LI5 and SI5.

Note 2: When the wrist is extended against resistance, the extensor digitorum tendon can be palpated more easily.

LU9: Taiyuan 太淵(淵)

On the anterolateral aspect of the wrist, between the radial styloid process and the scaphoid bone, in the depression ulnar to the abductor pollicis longus tendon.

Note: On the radial side of the palmar wrist crease, over the radial artery.

BL20: Pishu 脾俞(俞)

In the upper back region, at the same level as the inferior border of the spinous process of the 11th thoracic vertebra (T11), 1.5 B-cun lateral to the posterior median line.

BL23: Shenshu 腎俞 (俞)

In the lumbar region, at the same level as the inferior border of the spinous process of the second lumbar vertebra (L2), 1.5 B-cun lateral to the posterior median line.

BL25: Dachangshu 大腸俞 (俞)

In the lumbar region, at the same level as the inferior border of the spinous process of the fourth lumbar vertebra (L4), 1.5 B-cun lateral to the posterior median line.

Lower body points:

ST36: Zusanli 足三里

On the anterior aspect of the leg, on the line connecting ST35 with ST41, 3 B-cun inferior to ST35.

Note: ST36 is located on the tibialis anterior muscle.

SP6: Sanyinjiao 三陰(阴)交

On the tibial aspect of the leg, posterior to the medial border of the tibia, 3 B-cun superior to the prominence of the medial malleolus.

Note: 1 B-cun superior to KI8.

BL60: Kunlun 崑(昆)崙(崙, 仑)

On the posterolateral aspect of the ankle, in the depression between the prominence of the lateral malleolus and the calcaneal tendon.

KI3: Taixi 太谿(溪)

On the posteromedial aspect of the ankle, in the depression between the prominence of the medial malleolus and the calcaneal tendon.

ST41: Jiexi 解谿(溪)

On the anterior aspect of the ankle, in the depression at the centre of the front surface of the ankle joint, between the tendons of extensor hallucis longus and extensor digitorum longus.

Note: ST41 is located between two tendons on the dorsum of the foot which are more distinct when the ankle is in dorsiflexion, and is at the midpoint of the line connecting the prominences of the lateral malleolus and the medial malleolus.

BL36: Chengfu 承扶

In the buttock region, at the midpoint of the gluteal fold.

BL40: Weizhong 委中

On the posterior aspect of the knee, at the midpoint of the popliteal crease.

GB30: Huantiao 環(环)跳

In the buttock region, at the junction of the lateral one third and medial two thirds of the line connecting the prominence of the greater trochanter with the sacral hiatus.

Note: GB30 is easier to locate when the subject is lying on the side with the thigh flexed.

Remarks: Alternative location for GB30 - in the buttock region, at the junction of the lateral one third and medial two thirds of the distance between the prominence of the greater trochanter and the anterior superior iliac spine.

References

1. World Health Organization. WHO standard acupuncture point locations in the Western Pacific region. Manila: WHO Regional Office for the Western Pacific; 2008 2008. 9789290613831.